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EFFECT OF POSITIVE REINFORCEMENT COUNSELLING TECHNIQUE ON AGGRESSION AMONG POST-BASIC STUDENTS IN KANO METROPOLIS, KANO STATE

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Abstract

The study investigated the effect of positive reinforcement counselling technique on aggression among post-basic students in Kano Metropolis. The study employed a quasi-experimental research design specifically, pretest post-test non randomized control group design. Two objectives guided the study while two null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The population of the study consists of seventy six (76) students with aggression while the sample of thirty (30) were purposely drawn from two public secondary schools in kano metropolis, kano state. Data collection instrument titled 'Aggression Behaviour Scale' was employed for the study. The instrument was validated and attained content validation while reliability was obtained using split half method yielding reliability coefficient of 0.65. The data collected was analyzed using paired sample t-test. The finding reveals that positive reinforcement technique has significant effect on physical and in this study is effective counselling tool for addressing the physical and verbal dimensions of aggression among post-basic students. Based on the findings, counsellors are recommended to utilise positive reinforcement counselling technique on students found with symptoms of aggression.

Keywords: Aggression, Positive Reinforcement, Post-Basic

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Introduction

Aggression is a worrisome phenomenon as many schools seem to have a significant number of students with aggression especially among secondary students. The stress that students face, can make them aggressive and when they get aggressive, they won't be able to concentrate, also students lose the ability to concentrate on their lessons or classes as they will always concentrate on what is annoying them causing social withdrawal and isolation. Aggression is an action or conduct that is intended to cause harm, either physically, verbally, relational or instrumentally, to self or other person. Aggression may also be seen as any action with the intent to harm others resulting to injury or pain, the behaviour can manifest in different ways which includes physical, verbal, relational, and instrumental. The physical aggression are behaviours that causes physical harm to others characterized by hitting, biting, kicking, and also use of objects or weapons. Verbal aggression may be seen as communication verbally that can harm people through the use of words, tone and manner, it is characterized by insult, persistent criticism, threats, and name calling. Thus, aggression negatively affects the academic performance of the students, failure due to poor performance, peer rejection to the students who exhibit the symptoms of the behaviour, therefore contributing to lower grades. Additionally, victimized students of such behavior may experience anxiety, social isolation and withdrawal.

Aggression behaviour involves conflict between individuals of equal level". Whenever the term aggressive is used to describe a student's behavior, images of physical injury to another automatically come to mind. Aggressive behavior doesn't just violate social boundaries. It can also affect relationships and even have professional or legal consequences. Recognizing the ways aggression shows up in your life can help you take steps toward addressing it, along with anger and any other emotions that might play a part (Naoreen et al.2018). Aggression has been reported by Van (2017) to be a prevailing anti-social act affecting individuals on a daily basis. It is a negative stimulus to another person as it pertains to the intention of harming that person (with the expectation that the aversive stimulus will reach its destination). School violence and aggressive tendencies have become a social problem especially among secondary school students in the contemporary world.

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According to Kjærviik, and Bushman (2021) aggressive behaviour is an intentional act to cause harm to another person. This could be expressed more overtly, such as physically hitting someone, in verbal or relational contexts, and also as violence, bullying, and more like covert action, such as lying and stealing. Therefore, designing effective, reliable and empirically based classroom interventions is important to improve the academic performance and social development of students who manifest aggression characteristics. In this regard, counselling intervention may be one of the ways to assist such students, specifically using positive reinforcement and the role-play counselling technique in this study.

However, positive reinforcement is a counselling technique that encourages desired behaviours by providing reward following a behaviour. It also focuses on encouraging students by offering incentives to spur them on when they do well academically or demonstrate positive behavior which may also be in form of comment, clapping, hug, and a smile. In the context of post-basic school, positive reinforcement involves acknowledging and rewarding instances of positive behaviour, such as cooperation, empathy, sharing, and conflict resolution. For example, a teacher poses question to the students and receives a correct answer from them, it should be followed with a clap to strengthen further responses.

Meanwhile, most school administrators and teachers applied variety of disciplinary measures to tackle the problem of aggression among students in school. Nakpodia (2010) reported that such conventional approach measures include, kneeling down, head knocks, ear pulling, slapping, manual work, sweeping and tidying the school environment, sending out of class, writing impositions, flogging, suspension, expulsion and reporting to the police among others.

Statement of the Problem

Aggression is a disturbing issue that could place students, the school and even parents at risk. In kano metropolis, aggression among students especially at the post-basic stage is increasingly spreading due to their exposure to crime activities exhibited in the environment in which they found themselves. Therefore, the aggressors causing harm to themselves, and their peers and victims of such behaviour develop fear of going to school, feeling uncomfortable within the school environment and lack full

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concentration to the learning process. Consequently, aggression disrupts the enabling learning environment needed for optimal and meaningful activities for both the aggressor and the victim. Thus, the victims are stressed, saddled with school phobia, low self-concepts, full of anxiety and dejection, diminished interest in school activities among others, while the aggressor on his part develops inferiority complex and a sense of irrelevance.

Experience of the researcher has shown that students with symptoms of aggression in classroom are found with behaviours of bullying their colleagues, name calling, hitting others and smashing doors. Therefore, the negative consequence of these behaviours may distract the peaceful atmosphere of the classroom thereby making teaching and learning so difficult to accomplish. Hence, may invariably, lead to poor academic performance/achievement and poor social relationship. Additionally, students might exhibit different forms of aggression which include physical and verbal. Physical aggression is an act that is done with the intention to harm or cause pain to others physically and characterized by symptoms of hitting, punching, kicking and slapping. Verbal aggression is a behaviour that is exhibited verbally through the use of tone, abuse or harsh words which might cause harm. Hence, students who exhibit verbal aggression are found with the symptoms of calling names, bullying and teasing.

Consequently, parents and teachers are concerned with why such students behave aggressively, they resort to measures such as beating, kneeling down, and suspension from school, sending out of classroom, seeping school compound and the likes. Thus, despite all measures taken to curb the behaviour still persist because at that stage they feel powerful, strong, feeling inferior making the behaviour more rampant among secondary school students.

However, aggression need a serious attention in order to help the aggressors adjust and reduce such behaviour by learning appropriate skills and also allow their victims to be comfortable and safe in the school environment. Therefore, employing the use of behavioural counselling technique as well as designing effective treatment strategies for students that are found with the symptoms of aggression may be relevant. The present study explored the effect of positive reinforcement counselling technique on aggression among Post Basic students in kano metropolis.

Objectives of the Study

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The objectives of this study are to find out the:

1. Effect of positive reinforcement counselling technique on physical dimension of aggression among post-basic school students in Kano Metropolis, Kano State.
2. Effect of positive reinforcement counselling technique on verbal dimension of aggression among post-basic school students in Kano Metropolis, Kano State.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant effect pretest and post-test mean scores of physical dimension of aggression among post-basic students in Kano metropolis exposed to positive reinforcement.
2. There is no significant effect in the pretest and the post-test mean scores of verbal dimension of aggression among post-basic students in Kano metropolis exposed to positive reinforcement.

Methodology

The study employed a quasi-experimental research design specifically pre-test post-test non randomized control group design. The reason for selecting this design is that it has the advantage of testing the results obtained from the pre-test and post-test in order to determine the effectiveness or otherwise of the treatment when compared with pretest scores. The population of the study consists of all SSII students in Kano metropolis who exhibited the symptoms of aggression. According to a statistical report obtained from relevant authorities, there are two hundred and sixty (260) schools with a population estimate of seventy thousand two hundred and twenty one (70,221) SSII as obtained in (2024). Based on the population estimate, three hundred and eighty two (382) SSII were used as guided by Research Advisors (2006) for the identification of the target population, based on the returned instrument seventy six (76) SSII students were identified with aggression symptoms hence forming the population of this study. The population were both male and female with their age ranges between 15-17 years. The sample size consisted of (30) participants purposely sampled from two schools in Kano metropolis, Kano state where Okobiah (1991), Kolo (1992), Denga (1986) all recommends a minimum of ten (10) participants for group counselling.

An instrument titled 'Aggression Behaviour Scale' was adapted from Buss and Perry (1992) and used for data collection was subjected to content validation to ascertain its validity for use in the present study. A pilot test was conducted to obtain reliability of the instrument using split half method and the data collected was analyzed using

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Cronbach alpha thereby yielding coefficients of 0.65. Paired sample t-test was used to test the two hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. T-test was used because it is the appropriate tool for determining the difference between means of two groups (Gay, 2009).

Presentation of Results

H₀₁: There is no significant effect between pre-test and post-test mean scores of physical dimension of aggression among post basic students in Kano Metropolis exposed to positive reinforcement.

Table 1: Paired sample t-test for pre-test and post-test scores of physical dimension

Group	N	Mean	SD	P value	Decision
Pretest physical	15	16.867	4.34	.000	rejected
Posttest physical	15	11.533	3.87		

Source: Fieldwork

Table 1 presents the results for pretest and posttest mean scores of physical dimension of aggression among post basic students of Kano Metropolis, Kano State, Nigeria, exposed to positive reinforcement. Based on the calculated t-value of 7.608 and p-value of .000 with degree of freedom 14, it indicates that there is significant effect of positive reinforcement on physical dimension of aggression. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, there is no significant effect in the pretest and posttest mean scores on physical dimension of aggression among post basic students of Kano Metropolis, exposed to positive reinforcement, is rejected.

H₀₂: There is no significant effect in pretest and posttest mean scores of verbal dimension of aggression among post basic students of Kano Metropolis, Kano State exposed to positive reinforcement.

Table 2: Paired sample t-test for pre-test and post-test scores of physical dimension

Group	N	Mean	SD	P value	Decision
Pretest verbal	15	13.80	2.75	.000	rejected
Posttest verbal	15	9.33	1.76		

Source: Fieldwork

Table 2 presents the results for pretest and posttest mean scores of verbal dimension of aggression among post basic students of Kano Metropolis Kano State, exposed to positive reinforcement. Based on the calculated t-value of 8.238 and p-value of .000

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with degree of freedom 14, it indicates that there is significant effect of positive reinforcement on verbal dimension of aggression. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, there is no significant difference in the pretest and posttest mean scores on verbal dimension of aggression among post basic students of Kano Metropolis, Kano State exposed to positive reinforcement, is rejected.

Summary of Findings

The findings from the analyses are summarized as follows:

1. There is significant effect between pretest and posttest mean scores on physical dimension of aggression among post basic students of Kano Metropolis exposed to positive reinforcement based on the p-value .000 which is significant at .005 level of significance; this indicated that the treatment is effective on physical dimension.
2. There is significant effect between pretest and posttest mean scores on verbal dimension of aggression among post basic students of Kano Metropolis exposed to positive reinforcement based on the p-value .000 which is significant at .005 level of significance; this indicated that the treatment is effective on verbal dimension.

Discussion of Findings

The study investigated the effect of positive reinforcement technique among post-basic students in Kano metropolis, Kano State. The major finding of this study shows that positive reinforcement counselling technique had effect on the two dimensions of aggression (physical and verbal). The finding of the study is in line with the findings of Bakar and Nekah (2015) where it showed that positive reinforcement is effective in the reduction of disruptive behaviour and increased pupils concentration after intervention. However, studies by Mayowa (2021) showed that social skills training therapy can be a helpful intervention for students who are aggressive and findings revealed that social skills training therapy is effective in reduction of aggression among secondary school students. As such, this is in line with the present study.

The present study supports the study by Jaeti and Suwarjo (2022) where the findings showed that self-management technique group counselling is effective in reducing verbal and physical aggression in students. However, findings in the present study found out that positive reinforcement and role-play counselling techniques are effective in the reduction of both physical and verbal dimensions of aggression.

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The finding is in line with Bakar and Zainal (2020) in their studies on the effects of positive reinforcement technique on disruptive behaviour of ADHD, the results showed that there was a reduction in disruptive behaviour and also increased the pupil's concentration after the intervention.

Conclusions

Evidence from this study shows that positive reinforcement technique is effective in the treatment of aggression among post-basic students. Therefore, the use of positive reinforcement is effective in the treatment of both physical and verbal, dimensions of aggression. Hence, it is concluded that the positive reinforcement counselling technique used in this study is effective counselling tool for addressing the physical and verbal dimensions of aggression among post-basic students.

Recommendations from the Study

Consequent upon the findings of this study, it is recommended as follows:

1. Since the findings of this study reveal that positive reinforcement was found to have effect on physical and verbal aggression, school counsellors can expose students found with aggression to behavioural interventions such as positive reinforcement.
2. Teachers should be vigilant in observing students taking into cognizance the symptoms of both physical and verbal aggression so as to be able to identify and refer students with aggression early

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